

1 **Zbtb12 and Zbtb36 are nuclear factors that have likely cooperative functions with Hnf4a in thymic**
2 **instruction of tolerance to self by activation of hepatic TRA in the mTEC.**

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7 We identified Zbtb12 based on study of human iPS cells containing mutation in one copy of Hnf4a. An
8 interaction between Hnf4a and Zbtb12, independent of AIRE, was supported by systems biologic study of
9 Hnf4a network co-regulated genes. AIRE ^{-/-} mTEC were defective in Zbtb12 induction, indicating that
10 AIRE could support Zbtb12 induction in the murine thymus.

11 Citations

12 1. Kappes, D.J., He, X. and He, X., 2006. Role of the transcription factor Th-POK in CD4: CD8
13 lineage commitment. Immunological reviews, 209(1), pp.237-252.